

Design of M70 & M80 grade concrete by replacing cement content with fly-ash for High Rise buildings

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Abstract— In Metro cities, from early 2000 high rise building (HRB) construction is taken place very vastly. As residential plots are costly and expensive in big cities and to accommodate continuously growing population the development of HRB have become popular. For this purpose, high strength concrete and high strength steel is required, which is the need of today. To resist extremely high compressive load initiate in the core or shear walls and column, to optimize the thickness of core/shear wall and to minimize the size of column this high strength concrete is required to be design. However, while designing high strength concrete the comparison of cost and durability of HRB on the basis of material is taken into account. In the present study, design of M70 and M80 grade concrete of HRB is carried out to determine optimum mix design and investigate slump by substituting cement content by different percentage of fly-ash (i.e. 15%, 20% and 25%). Results indicate that, the compressive strength of M70 and M80 grade concrete increases by 20% and 12.75% respectively than the required strength. By replacing cement content with FA by 15%, 20% and 25% the average compressive strength is 84.24 MPa for M80 grade concrete. The study concludes that, no significant increase in compressive strength is observed by replacing the cement content

Keywords— High Rise Building (HRB), High strength concrete, concrete mix design, Fly-ash (FA), Workability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete has been in use as a major building material ever since its inception. World over, last three-four decades have seen construction of innumerable reinforced concrete structures with compressive strength of concrete in the range of 60–100 MPa. The main cause of concern is the non-renewable nature of natural sand and the corresponding increasing demand of construction industry, therefore looking for an alternative to river sand has become a necessity. The cheapest and easiest alternative to natural sand is manufacturing sand by crushing rocks or stones in desired size and grade by suitable method. Sand produced by such means is known as manufactured or crusher or artificial sand. Concrete, an artificial stone-like mass, is the composite material that is created by mixing binding material (cement or lime) along with the aggregate (sand, gravel, stone, brick chips, etc.), water, admixtures, etc. in specific proportions. There are different grades of concrete and its classification is depending upon the grades itself. The different grades and its classification is briefly explained in the following section [2].

- a) High-strength concrete (HSC): It is a type of concrete with high compressive strength compared to normal-strength concrete (NSC). Although there is no exact limit of compressive strength that could distinguish HSC from NSC, the American Concrete Institute defines High strength concrete with a compressive strength of more than 60MPa. The compressive strength of hardened concrete which is generally considered to be an index of its other properties, depends upon many factors, e.g. quality and quantity of cement, water and aggregates; batching and mixing; placing, compaction

and curing. The cost of concrete is made up of the cost of materials, plant and labour. The variations in the cost of materials arise from the fact that the cement is several times costly than the aggregate, thus the aim is to produce as lean a mix as possible. From technical point of view the rich mixes may lead to high shrinkage and cracking in the structural concrete, and to evolution of high heat of hydration in mass concrete which may cause cracking [11,12].

- b) High performance concrete (HPC): For concrete mixtures possessing high workability, high durability and high ultimate strength. Concrete, whose ingredients, proportions and production methods are specifically chosen to meet special performance and uniformity requirements that cannot be always achieved routinely by using only conventional materials, like, cement, aggregates, water and chemical admixtures, and adopting normal mixing, placing and curing practices. These performance requirements can be high strength, high early strength, high workability, low permeability and high durability for severe service environments, etc. or combinations thereof. In the other words a HPC is a concrete in which certain characteristics are developed for a particular application and environment, so that it will give excellent performance in the structure in which it will be placed, in the environment to which it will be exposed, and with the loads to which it will be subjected during its design life. It includes concrete that provides either substantially improved resistance to environmental influences (durability in service) or substantially increased structural capacity while maintaining adequate durability. It may also include concrete, which significantly reduces construction time without compromising long-term serviceability. While high strength concrete, aims at enhancing strength and consequent advantages owing to improved strength, the term high- performance concrete (HPC) is used to refer to concrete of required performance for the majority of construction applications without compromising long-term serviceability. While high strength concrete, aims at enhancing strength and consequent advantages owing to improved strength, the term high-performance concrete (HPC) is used to refer to concrete of required performance for the majority of construction applications. Table 1 indicates different grades of concrete and its compressive strength [13].

TABLE I
CONCRETE GRADES

Sr. No	Classification	Grade of Concrete	Compressive Strength
1	Normal Strength Concrete	M5	5 MPA
		M10	10 MPA
		M15	15 MPA
		M20	20 MPA
2	Standard Strength Concrete	M25	25 MPA
		M30	30 MPA
		M35	35 MPA
		M40	40 MPA
3	High Strength Concrete	M45	45 MPA
		M50	50 MPA
		M55	55 MPA
		M60	60 MPA
		M65	65 MPA
		M70	70 MPA

As per Indian Standard code of practice (IS 4926) Ready Mixed Concrete (RMC) is defined as “The concrete delivered in plastic condition and requiring no further treatment before being placed in position in which it is to set and harden. Instead of being batched and mixed on site, concrete is delivered for placing from central batching plant”. RMC is a specialized material in which the cement aggregates and other ingredients are weigh-batched at a plant in a central mixer or truck mixer, before delivery to the construction site in a condition ready for placing by the builder. Thus, `fresh' concrete is manufactured in a plant away from the construction site and transported within the requisite journey time. Additionally, transit-mixing allows concrete to be hauled to construction sites further away from the plant. These plants are generally available in capacities varying from 15 cum/hour to 200 cum/hour. Further, fly ash use can

greatly improve pump ability while enhancing the quality of the concrete and controlling costs. Figure 1 shows the typical overview of RMC plant.

Figure 1: Typical overview of RMC plant

(Source: <https://constrofacilitator.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/ranninfra.jpg>)

A. Properties of High-Performance Concrete

The properties of HPC are discussed briefly below.

- High modulus of elasticity.
- High abrasion resistance.
- High durability and long life in severe environments.
- Low permeability and diffusion.
- Resistance to chemical attack.
- High resistance to frost and deicer scaling damage.
- Toughness and impact resistance.
- Ease of placement.
- Chemical Attack.
- Carbonation.

B. Parameters of High-Performance Concrete

Permeation is a major factor that causes premature deterioration of concrete structures. The provision of high-performance concrete must center on minimizing permeation through proportioning methods and suitable construction procedures (curing) to ensure that the exposure conditions do not cause ingress of moisture and other agents responsible for deterioration. It is important to identify the dominant transport phenomenon and design the mix proportion with the aim of reducing that transport mechanism which is dominant to a predefined acceptable performance limit based on permeability.

The parameter to be controlled for achieving the required performance criteria could be any of the following.

- a) Water/ (cement + mineral admixture) ratio.
- b) Strength.
- c) Densification of cement paste.
- d) Elimination of bleeding.
- e) Homogeneity of the mix.
- f) Particle size distribution.
- g) Dispersion of cement in the fresh mix.
- h) Stronger transition zone.
- i) Low free lime content.
- j) Very little free water in hardened concrete.

C. Methods of concrete mix design

The methods used for the design of various grades of concrete are mentioned in the following section.

1. American Method of Mix Design
2. Graphic Method of Mix Design
3. Mix Design by Indian Standard Method
4. American Concrete Institute Method of Mix Design
5. Rapid Method of Mix Design

In the present study mix design is carried out by using Indian standard method.

D. Design Criterion as per Indian Standard Code for Practice

The criteria for the mix design is given by I. S code which is briefly explained in figure 2.

Figure 2: Criteria used for the design of concrete

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been various studies took place that have been carried out to find out the compressive strength of high strength concrete. Various methods adopted to carry out the strength like change in w/c ratio, change in the percentage of fly ash.

Maiti “et al.” (2006) gave relationships between water-cement ratios or water cementitious materials ratios and 28-day compressive strength for concrete containing OPC or PPC or (OPC + fly ash) and a super-plasticizer. Bentz (2009) studied the Properties that are critical to the early-age performance of materials used in concrete are tested, including heat release, semi-adiabatic temperature, setting time, autogenously deformation, and strength development. Pathak and Deshpande (2005) studied the dimensional analysis method for predicting the 28-day compressive strength of 53-grade cement. N. P. Rajamane (2006) have studied fly ash (FA) as a cementitious material extensively and it is observed that FA refines the microstructure of Portland cement matrix and thereby enhancing the durability. Goyal “et al.” (2007) - Role of fly ash addition on superplasticizer dosage, slump, and 28 day and 90 day compressive strength of silica fume concrete is investigated in this work. Three water to binder ratios, ranging from 0.45 to 0.25, representing moderate to high strength concrete are considered. Mixes containing binary and ternary cementitious composition of ordinary Portland cement, silica fume and fly ash are investigated. It is demonstrated that fly ash incorporation in OPC silica fume concrete leads to reduction in superplasticizer dosage. Ozlem Celik “et al.” (2008) - in this paper results indicate that’s fly ash samples in ratio of 15% in clinker markedly increases in the compressive strength value. The fineness is a more effective parameter than chemical composition in improving the strength development of fly ash mortars. When type C and type F fly ash fineness properties are improved, higher compressive strength values can be obtained by preparing different mixtures. M. R. Karim “et al.” (2011) the better performances of ashes and their pozzolanic activity are usually related with the more spherical shape and smooth feature of fly ash as compared to cement particles. The fineness effect of fly ash on strength of mortar and concrete. T. P. SINGH (2007) studied that a concrete having a low water content and in which at least 50% of the Portland cement is replaced by a good quality fly ash. This concrete also contains a superplasticizer which helps reduce water while providing the needed workability. The HVFAC could achieve better performance than expected using only half of the conventional OPC thus saving GHG emissions of nearly 200 kg for every m³ of concrete used. The permeability and hence the durability characteristics of HVFAC are far more superior to plain concrete.

III.METHODOLOGY

Design of M70 and M80 grade concrete of HRB is carried out to determine optimum mix design and investigate slump by substituting cement content by different percentage of fly-ash (i.e. 15%, 20% and 25%). The study is carried out by adopting following methodology.

- a) To obtain physical properties of fly ash IS code of fly ash by referring IS 3812:2012.
- b) Carrying out experimental tests in laboratory on the FA (fineness test by Blaine's air permeability test, sieve analysis, lime reactivity test, soundness test and specific gravity)
- c) Design of M70 and M80 grade Concrete using I. S. code method.
- d) Determination of slump at different percentage of fly-ash (15%, 20% and 25%).

IV. DESIGN OF M70 AND M80 GRADE CONCRETE

The design of M70 and M80 grade concrete is carried out replacing cement content by different percentage of fly-ash (15%, 20% and 25%) and determined the optimum mix design. Several mix design calculations have been done to get targeted mean compressive strength of concrete. Considering 15%, 20% and 25% of fly ash with varying water cement ratio is adopted to get desired or required workability at pumping location. In addition to that the workability of concrete is checked after the interval of every 30min. post preparation of mix.

A. Laboratory tests on Fly-ash

Different experimental tests are carried out in the laboratory to investigate the physical properties of fly-ash such as fineness test (Blaine's air permeability test), sieve analysis, lime reactivity test, soundness test and specific gravity. The tests are carried out by referring I. S. 1727: 1967 (reaffirmed 2008).

B. Design of concrete (I. S. code method)

By referring I. S. code, the design of M70 and M80 grade concrete is carried out replacing cement content by different percentage of fly-ash (15%, 20% and 25%) and determined the optimum mix design.

A. Design of M70 grade concrete

The mix proportion and its stipulations for M70 grade concrete are considered referring the I. S. 10262: 2019 provisions and are mentioned in the following Table no II.

TABLE II
M70 GRADE MIX DESIGN CALCULATIONS

DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS		
1	Grade designation	M70
2	Characteristic compressive strength of concrete at 28 days (f _{ck})	M70
3	Type of cement	OPC 53 grade
4	Maximum nominal size of aggregate	20 mm
5	Minimum cement content (As Per IS 456: 2000)	360kg
6	Maximum water-cement ratio (As Per IS 456: 2000)	0.40
7	Workability for Pumping/Manual at Pouring point as per standard IS-4926 it shall be	550 +/-50mm
8	Exposer condition (As Per IS 456: 2000)	Severe
9	Method of concrete placing	Manual/Pumping
10	Degree of supervision (As per Table 1 of 10262:1982)	Good
11	Type of aggregate	Crushed angular aggregate
12	Grading of Fine aggregate (As per 383:1970)	Zone II
13	Chemical admixture type (As per 9103:1999)	Superplasticizer
14	Tolerance factor (As Per IS 456: 2000)	1.65
15	Standard deviation for good control of specified grade of concrete (s)(As per Table 1 of IS 10262:1982)	6 MPa
TARGET MEAN STRENGTH		
1	Target average 28 days compressive strength of concrete (f _{ck}) specified characteristic cube strength (f _{ck} =f _{ck} +t*s)	79.90MPa for tolerance (risk factor) 1.65, the target mean strength of the specified characteristic cube strength (f _{ck} = f _{ck} +t*s)
SELECTION OF WATER CEMENT RATIO		
2	Max. water-cement ratio for R.C.C Table 5 (as per IS:456-2000)	0.4
3	Based on trial with superplasticizer Water-cement ratio adopted	0.22
4	Water Content	158Kg/Cum
CALCULATION OF CEMENT CONTENT		
1	Water-cement ratio	0.22
2	Cementitious content	780 Kg/Cum
3	From Table 5 of IS 456, minimum cement content for severe exposure	360 Kg/Cum

	condition is	
4	710 Kg is greater than 360 Kg Hence, O.K	
5	Flyash content of total cementitious material % is 20	160 Kg/Cum
6	Cement Content (OPC)	480 Kg/Cum
7	Micro silica content of total cementitious material % is 9.86	70 Kg/Cum

After the calculations as per IS code method following mix proportion summary is obtained for one cubic meter of concrete and presented in Table no. III.

TABLE III
DESIGN CALCULATIONS FOR M70 GRADE CONCRETE

Sr. No.	Mix proportion for one cubic meter of concrete (M70)	Weight (Kg/Cu. m)
1	Cement	450
2	Fly ash	93
3	Micro silica	55
4	Crush Sand	780.61
6	Coarse aggregate content 10mm	401.6
7	Coarse aggregate content 20mm	484.95
8	Water content	186.36
9	Chemical admixture	8.52
10	Super plasticizer	7.05
11	Retarder	4.94
12	Total density of concrete	2463

B. Design of M80 grade concrete

The mix proportion and its stipulations for M80 grade concrete are considered referring the I. S. 10262: 2019 provisions and are mentioned in the following Table no IV.

TABLE IV
DESIGN CALCULATIONS FOR M80 GRADE CONCRETE

Sr. No	Mix proportion for one cubic meter of concrete (M80)	Weight (Kg/Cu. m)
1	Cement	480
3	Fly ash	220
4	Micro silica	60
6	Crush Sand	624.62
7	Coarse aggregate content 10mm	400.87
8	Coarse aggregate content 20mm	508.96
9	Water content	178.55
10	Super plasticizer	8.40
11	Retarder	2.66
12	Total density of concrete	2484

C. Concrete cubes casting and testing

The following procedure is adopted for the casting of concrete cubes

Fig. 3 Material Weighing

Fig. 4 Material Mixing

Fig. 5 Workability by flow table and slump cone

Fig. 6 Cube Casting

Fig.7 Curing of concrete cubes

Fig. 8 CTM

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The design of M70 and M80 grade concrete which is carried out replacing cement content by different percentage of fly-ash (15%, 20% and 25%) and determined the optimum mix design is explained in detail.

A. Physical properties of fly ash

For carrying out mix design the physical properties of fly-ash such as fineness test (Blaine’s air permeability test), sieve analysis, lime reactivity test, soundness test and specific gravity are investigated. The results of the fly-ash are represented in tabular form in table 5

TABLE V
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF FLY ASH

Sr. No.	Tests	Results	Requirements (as per IS:3812(pt. 1) 2013)	Conformity	Protocol
	Physical properties				
1	Fineness (Specific surface), M2/kg (Blaine's air permeability method)	320.8	320 min	Yes	IS 1727-1967 (Reaffirmed 2008)
2	Particle retained on 45micron IS sieve, % by mass (Wet sieving)	16.4	34 max	Yes	IS 1727-1967 (Reaffirmed 2008)
3	Lime reactivity Average comp strength N/mm2	4.6	4.5 min	Yes	IS 1727-1967 (Reaffirmed 2008)
4	Soundness Auto clave expansion (%)	0.04	0.8 max	Yes	IS 1727-1967 (Reaffirmed 2008)
5	Specific Gravity	2.12	NA	NA	NA

B. Design of Concrete to determine compressive strength

For the determination of average compressive strength of concrete the design of M70 and M80 grade concrete is carried out and tested after 3 days, 7 days and 28 days. The brief results are tabulated and discussed in the following sections.

A. Design of M70 grade concrete

The results for the design of M70 grade concrete is tabulated and represented in Table no. VI

TABLE VI
DESIGN RESULTS FOR M70 GRADE CONCRETE

Concrete grade	M70					
Material	Type			Source		
Cement	Ultra cement 53 Grade			Gujarat		
GGBS	JSW			PEN		
Micro silica	Elkem					
Flyash	Ash tech			Dhanu/nashik		
Cr. Sand	Crushed Sand (VSI)			URAN		
10mm	Crushed Basalt (VSI)			URAN		
20mm	Crushed Basalt (VSI)			URAN		
Super plasticizer	CAC hyper fluid			CAC		
Retarder	CAC RETARDPLAST			CAC		
Moisture content & water absorption						
Material	10mm	20mm	wash sand	C.SAND		
Surface moisture	0.50%	0.50%	0.00%	2.50%		
ABSORPTION (for SSD)	1.52%	1.48%	0.00%	4.25%		
			Batch Vol. M3	0.05		
Ingredients	Units		SSD batch weight per m ³	Correction	Corrected batch	Trial batch
Cement OPC	Kg		450		450.00	22.50
Fly ash	Kg		93		93	4.65
Micro silica	Kg		60		55.00	2.750
C.sand	Kg		793	12.390	780.61	39.03
Coarse 1 (10mm)	Kg		405	3.937	401.06	20.05
Coarse 2 (20mm)	Kg		490	5.047	484.95	24.24
Water	Kg		165	21.36	186.36	9.31
Super plasticizer	Kg	1.00%	7.05		7.05	0.353
Retarder	Kg	0.70%	4.94		4.94	0.247
Density			2468		2463	
Workability test			Temperature	Remarks		
Slump/ flow test	Initial	680MM		09 cubes casted		
	60min	660MM				
	120 min	620MM				
	180min	580MM				
Compressive strength						
Age (days)	Weight (Kg)		Load (KN)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Average Strength (MPa)	
3	8.560		1237.6	55.00	56.36	
	8.500		1300.9	57.82		
	8.420		1266.1	56.27		
7	8.460		1835.6	81.58	80.09	
	8.560		1769.5	78.64		
	8.500		1800.9	80.04		
28	8.700		2010.5	89.36	87.88	
	8.500		1951.1	86.72		
	8.540		1970.0	87.56		

From Table VI it is clear that the compressive strength of the concrete goes on increasing right from day 3 to day 28.

Fig. 9 Increase in compressive strength of concrete for M70 grade concrete

From fig. 9 it is clear that after 3 days, 7 days and 28 days the average compressive strength of concrete is 56.36 MPa, 80.09 MPa and 87.88 MPa respectively. 20% increase in compressive strength is observed for M70 grade concrete than the required strength as per I. S. Code. Further, the strength of concrete increases 30% from day 3 to day 7.

B. Design of M80 grade concrete

The results for the design of M80 grade concrete is tabulated and represented in Table no. VII

TABLE VII
DESIGN RESULTS FOR M80 GRADE CONCRETE

Concrete grade	M80					
Material	Type			Source		
Cement	Ultra cement 53 grade			GUJARAT		
GGBS	JSW			PEN		
Micro silica	Elkem					
Flyash	Ash tech			DHANU/NASHIK		
Cr. Sand	Crushed Sand (VSI)			URAN		
10mm	Crushed Basalt (VSI)			URAN		
20mm	Crushed Basalt (VSI)			URAN		
Super plasticizer	CAC HYPERFLUID			CAC		
Retarder	CAC RETARDPLAST			CAC		
Moisture content & water absorption						
Material	10mm	20mm	wash sand	C.SAND		
Surface moisture	1.00%	1.00%	0.00%	2.00%		
Absorption (for SSD)	1.52%	1.48%	0.00%	4.25%		
			Batch Vol. M3	0.04		
Ingredients	Units		SSD batch weight per m ³	Correction	Corrected batch	Trial batch
Cement opc	Kg		480		480.00	19.200
Flyash	Kg		72		220.00	2.880
GGBS	Kg		220		00.00	00
Microsilica	Kg		60		60.00	2.400
C.sand	Kg		639	14.378	624.62	24.985
Coarse 1 (10mm)	Kg		405	4.131	400.87	16.035
Coarse 2 (20mm)	Kg		514	5.037	508.96	20.359
Water	Kg		155	23.546	178.55	7.142
Super plasticizer	Kg	1.10%	8.40		8.40	0.336
Retarder	Kg	0.35%	2.66		2.66	0.106

Density		2484		2484	
Workability test		Temperature		Remarks	
Slump/ flow test	Initial	700MM		09 cubes casted	
	60min	660MM			
	120min	650MM			
	180min	620MM			
COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH					
Age	Weight Kg	Load KN	Strength MPa	Avg. Strength in MPa	
3	8.260	1098.6	48.83	46.24	
	8.420	1035.9	46.04		
	8.600	986.6	43.85		
7	8.660	1772.8	78.79	77.79	
	8.620	1749.3	77.75		
	8.660	1729.0	76.84		
28	8.660	2053.3	91.26	91.70	
	8.640	2110.7	93.81		
	8.700	2025.7	90.03		

From Table VII it is clear that the compressive strength of the concrete goes on increasing right from day 3 to day 28.

Fig. 10 Increase in compressive strength of concrete for M80 grade concrete

From fig. 10 it is clear that after 3 days, 7 days and 28 days the average compressive strength of concrete is 46.24 MPa, 77.79 MPa and 91.70 MPa respectively. 12.75% increase in compressive strength is observed for M80 grade concrete than the required strength as per I. S. Code. It is also seen that the strength of concrete increases 40.55% from day 3 to day 7.

C. Design of concrete with varying percentage of fly ash

The concrete of M80 grade is considered for further replacement of cement since the compressive strength of M80 grade give better results as compared to M80 grade concrete. Therefore, the design of M80 grade concrete is done replacing cement content by 15%, 20% and 25% respectively. The results for the design are tabulated and expressed in the following sections.

TABLE VIII
WHEN CEMENT IS REPLACED WITH FLY ASH BY 15%

Raw material	SSD Mix Design	Absorption	Abs Water	Dry Mix Design
OPC 53	450			450
Fly Ash	93			93
Micro Silica	60			60
20 mm	490	1.70%	8	481
10 mm	405	1.79%	7	398
R. Sand	0	0.00%	0	0
Cr. Sand	793	3.75%	30	764
Water	165		45	210

TABLE IX
WHEN CEMENT IS REPLACED WITH FLY ASH BY 20%

Raw Material	SSD Mix Design	Absorption	Abs Water	Dry Mix Design
OPC 53	450			450
Fly ash	142			142
Micro Silica	60			60
20 mm	472	1.70%	8	464
10 mm	391	1.79%	7	384
R. Sand	0	0.00%	0	0
Cr. Sand	765	3.75%	29	736
Water	165		44	209

TABLE X
WHEN CEMENT IS REPLACED WITH FLY ASH BY 25%

Raw Material	SSD Mix Design	Absorption	Abs Water	Dry Mix Design
OPC 53	450			450
fly Ash	175			175
Micro Silica	60			60
20 mm	460	1.70%	8	452
10 mm	381	1.79%	7	374
R. Sand	0	0.00%	0	0
Cr. Sand	745	3.75%	28	718
Water	165		43	208

D. Comparison for design results of replacement of cement with fly ash by varying percentage
The mix design is carried out by replacing cement content by fly-ash (15%,20% and 25%). The comparative results are displayed in the fig. 11.

Fig. 11 Comparison of results for different percentage of fly-ash.

E. Impact of fly ash on workability of concrete

The mix design is carried out by replacing cement content by fly-ash (15%,20% and 25%). By replacing cement content, the percentage of cementitious binding material get reduces and ultimately effects on strength of concrete. On the other hand, the workability of the concrete get automatically increases. The results for the same is indicated in fig. 12.

Fig. 12 Comparison of results for different percentage of fly-ash

VI. CONCLUSION

The design of M70 and M80 grade concrete is carried out by replacing cement content with fly-ash of varying percentage (15%,20% and 25%). The mix design is performed referring I.S. code provisions and the limiting values required for different grades. The conclusions drawn from the study is explained in detail.

- 1) The results obtained from the laboratory tests (i.e. fineness test (Blaine's air permeability test), sieve analysis, lime reactivity test, soundness test and specific gravity) which are carried out to determine the physical properties of fly-ash are within the limit of I. S. 3812 (part-I): 2013.
- 2) After 3 days, 7 days and 28 days the compressive strength of concrete for M70 grade is 56.36 MPa, 80.09 MPa and 87.88 MPa respectively. The maximum compressive strength of M70 grade concrete gained after 28 days is 87.88 MPa. There is 20% increase in strength for M70 grade concrete than the required compressive strength. However, the compressive strength of concrete increases 30% from day 3 to day 7.
- 3) After 3 days, 7 days and 28 days the compressive strength of concrete for M80 grade is 46.24 MPa, 77.79 MPa and 91.70 MPa respectively. The maximum compressive strength of M80 grade concrete gained after 28 days is 91.70 MPa. There is 12.75% increase in strength for M80 grade concrete than the required compressive strength. It is also observed that the strength of M80 grade concrete increases 40.55% from day 3 to day 7.
- 4) When cement is replaced with fly-ash by 15%, 20% and 25% the workability of concrete is 600mm, 620mm and 650mm respectively. Further, no significant increase in compressive strength is observed by replacing the cement content. The average compressive strength is 84.24 MPa. By replacing cement content with fly-ash by varying percentage (i.e. 15%, 20% and 25%), the percentage of cementitious binding material get reduces and ultimately effect on compressive strength of concrete. On the other hand, the workability of the concrete get automatically increases.

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VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] N.G. Gore and S.K. Ukarande, "Performance of Dual-Outrigger Structural System in Geometrically Irregular Shaped High-Rise Building," *International Journal of Engineering Science Invention*, vol. 8, pp. 16-35, May 2019.
- [2] Maiti S C "et al". "Concrete mix proportioning" *The Indian Concrete Journal*, December 2006.
- [3] Dale P. "et al". "Early age properties of cement based materials. II: Influence of water to cement ratio" *Journal of materials in Civil Engineering* 21(9):512:517, September 2009.
- [4] Dr. D. R. Pathak and N. P. Deshpande, "Experimental Study Report on Use of Fly Ash In Ready Mixed Concrete", *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2012.
- [5] N. P. Rajmane, Fly Ash (FA) as a "Cementitious Material has been Studied Extensively and it is Observed that FA refines the Microstructure of Portland Cement Matrix and thereby Enhancing the Durability" *Cement and Concrete Composites*, Vol 29, Issue 3 Mar 2007, Pg 218-223.
- [6] Ozlem Celik, "et al". "Characterization of fly ash and its effects on the compressive strength properties of Portland cement.", *Indian Journal of Engineering and Materials Sciences*, IJEMS Vol.15(5) October 2008.
- [7] M. R. Karim "et al". "Strength development of mortar and concrete containing fly ash", *International Journal of the Physical Sciences*, Vol. 6(17), pp. 4137-4153, 2 September, 2011.
- [8] T.P.SINGH, "FIELD PERFORMANCE OF HIGH VOLUME FLY ASH CONCRETE", *Paper presented at 9th CANMET / ACI Int'l conference in Poland* - May 2007.
- [9] Shweta Goyal "et al". "Potential benefits of incorporating fly ash in silica fume concrete", *Institute of Engg. Journal CV* Vol 88 May 2007.
- [10] M. Collepardi, "Admixtures used to enhance placing characteristics of concrete", *Cement & Concrete Composite*, Vol. 20, 1998, 103-112
- [11] Farny and Panarese, "High strength concrete", *Portland cement association, Engineering bulletin*, 1994.
- [12] S.A.Hussaini, "Use of high strength concrete grades for buildings and towers", *International research journal of Engineering and Technology, IRJET*, Volume: 07 Issue: 12, Dec 2020.
- [13] Anant Kumar "et al.", "HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE & ITS APPLICATIONS IN CIVIL ENGG", *International journal of advance research in science and engineering*, volume no 6, special issue no (02), September 2017.
- [14] IS 456:2000 Plain and reinforced concrete – Code of practise
- [15] IS 10262:2019 Concrete mix proportioning- Guidelines.
- [16] SP 24(S&T):1983- Explanatory Handbook on Indian Standard code of practice for plain and reinforced concrete.
- [17] IS 4926: 2003 and 2009, "Indian Standard Code of Practice for Ready Mixed Concrete", (2nd revision) Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi.
- [18] IS 3812:2013, "Pulverized fly ash-Specifications.
- [19] Literatures.
- [20] M. S. Shetty, *Concrete Technology*, 15th Ed.